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Development Of A Model Of Multimedia Presentation For The Formation Of Sound Analysis And Synthesis In Primary School Students With Speech Disorders

Nazarova Madinabonu Ulugbek kizi

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Abstract: The article presents a theoretical analysis of the concept of a "model" and substantiates the need to develop a pedagogical model of a multimedia presentation for the formation of sound analysis and synthesis in primary schoolchildren with speech disorders. The essential properties and categorical features of the model are defined, and classifications of pedagogical models in the works of domestic researchers are reviewed. As the basis for the development of the multimedia presentation, content-based and pragmatic types of models were selected. The principles of multimedia presentation construction (dynamism, systematization, differentiated approach, and visibility) are described, as well as the slide structure, which includes the title, methodological and technical information, tasks, types of assistance, and encouragement. An algorithm of a speech therapist's work on creating educational exercises in PowerPoint is proposed, which contributes to the effective formation of sound analysis and synthesis, increases motivation, and improves students' concentration. The developed model not only optimizes the process of creating multimedia presentations but also enhances the quality of correctional work with children with speech disorders.

Keywords: model, pedagogical model, multimedia presentation, sound analysis, sound synthesis, students with speech disorders, speech therapy, correctional teaching.

Introduction.

In order to competently develop a model of a multimedia presentation for the development of sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments, it is necessary to find out what a model is. It should be noted that the concept of "model" has various definitions and its understanding in science differs significantly.

Having analyzed literary sources [1, 3, 4, 6], the following definitions of the concept of "model" were identified:

1) a "quadruple" design that includes the following components: a subject, a task solved by the subject, an original object and a description language or a method of material reproduction of the model [3];

2) such a materially realized or mentally represented system that, displaying or reproducing the object of study, is able to replace it so that its study provides

new information about this object [6];

3) a structure transferred from one subject to another and embodied in it in a real and technically accurate manner [2]; 4) a system selected or created by a subject that reproduces the aspects (structural parts, relationships, properties, parameters) of the object being studied that are essential for the set goal of knowledge, and, as a result, is in such a relationship of similarity and substitution with it that its study serves as an indirect way of obtaining knowledge about this object;

5) this is a system, the study of which serves as a means of obtaining information about another system.

The following definitions of the concept of "model" can be found in dictionaries [5, 6]: 1) an abstract concept of a standard or sample of any system, a representation of the most general characteristics of any phenomenon; 2) a diagram or sample of any unit showing the sequential arrangement of its constituent parts.

It should be noted that, like any system, a model has properties inherent to it. Thus, it was revealed that a model has several groups of essential properties [3]:

- subjectivity (this means that the researcher independently selects the properties in which this model corresponds to the original);

- dual nature (this means that the model is both a means of cognition and an object of research, because during the study it replaces the object, but at the same time the model retains most of the features important for the researcher and becomes an object of research);

- compactness (this means that the model recreates the object of research in an elementary form, therefore it is more compact than the original);

- transformability (this means that various manipulations can be performed with the model that cannot be done with the original);

- specific information content of the model as a means of cognition (this means that in the model it is always possible to identify properties that are not represented in the original object, since it always appears in an abstract form).

It was also revealed that the model has categorical features that characterize it [4]:

1) the model replaces the object of study, which was created for the purpose of studying the object;

2) the model provides information about the object;

3) the model is in a relationship of analogy with the original object;

4) unlike a copy of an object, the model repeats the object one-sidedly and

incompletely: in any of its aspects or several aspects;

5) the model has such characteristics as clarity and compactness, which allows you to capture the object with a single mental gaze.

Speaking about the pedagogical model, it is necessary to note the work of Yu.O. Delimova, in which she defines the pedagogical model as “an artificially created object in the form of physical structures, diagrams, formulas or symbolic forms, which, being similar to the phenomenon (or object) under study, reproduces and displays in a simplified form the structure, interrelations, properties and relationships between the parts of this object (or phenomenon)” [1].

She proposed the following types of pedagogical models depending on the target orientation [1]:

- training models (simulators, visual aids and training programs);
- experimental models (such models are also called natural and are used to study an object and predict its structure, properties and characteristics);
- scientific and technical models (such models are created to study phenomena and processes);
- game models (economic, military, sports, business games:
 - these models recreate the behavioral characteristics of an object in different situations, taking into account possible reactions from a competitor, enemy or ally);
- simulation models (such models reproduce the characteristics of the object under study, preserving the exact internal relationship between the elements of the system, and do not simply reflect reality with any degree of accuracy).

The definition of the concept of "pedagogical model" is also found in such an author as E.A. Lodatko: a pedagogical model is a thinking system that imitates or reflects certain properties, attributes and characteristics of the object of study, the principles of its internal organization or functioning, and presents it in the form of a cultural form inherent in a certain socio-cultural practice [3].

He proposes a classification of pedagogical models depending on the subject of modeling, which includes structure, content and functionality. According to the presented subjects, the author defines the following basic types of pedagogical models [3]:

1. Content models. This is a type of models for which the subject of modeling is the content of the object under study, formed by a set of certain attributes (characteristics, features, properties, etc.), which serve as the basis for its specification.

2. Structural models. This is a type of models for which the subject of

modeling is the structure of the object under study, determined by the principles of internal organization, together with the connections characteristic of its components.

3. Functional models. This is a type of models for which the subject of modeling is the orientation of the object under study to the implementation of specific, pedagogically significant functions.

It should be noted that in addition to the basic models, there are derivative types of pedagogical models. It is the basic types of pedagogical models that are the basis for the formation of derivative types, the basis of which is formed by a dual subject of modeling: content and structure, or functionality and structure, or functionality and content of the object of study. Thus, the following derivative types are distinguished: structural-content, structural-functional, functional-content.

It should be noted that there is another approach that determines the typology of models depending on the problem being solved. In accordance with two tasks (constructive and expert), two types of models are distinguished [3]:

1. Pragmatic model. Such a model is characterized as a means of organizing actions; a model with a given property is created to solve a constructive problem.

2. Cognitive model. Such a model is a form of presenting and organizing knowledge, a means of connecting new knowledge with existing knowledge; a model with a given property is created to solve an expert problem.

The modeling process consists of stages that are built depending on the type of model, since further work is significantly different [3]. However, it should be noted that the zero stage is included in the modeling process when constructing any type of models, since it involves setting the problem. Then, after setting the problem, the modeling object and the type of model (pragmatic or cognitive) are determined - this is where the differences appear.

Thus, based on the typology of pedagogical models proposed by E.A. Lodatko, to build a model of a multimedia presentation for the formation of sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments, we selected the content and pragmatic types of models.

Based on the fact that the subject of modeling is the content of a multimedia presentation, which will be used by speech therapists in remedial classes, the developed model is meaningful. In our opinion, familiarizing speech therapists with the content of a multimedia presentation will contribute to the effective formation of sound analysis and synthesis, focusing children's attention on the lesson, and increasing motivation.

It should be noted that when creating a multimedia presentation for use in

developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments, a number of principles were relied upon, which acted as requirements for a competent presentation structure:

- the principle of dynamism (implies the ability to make additions and changes to the content of the presentation, which allow improving the techniques presented to students; as well as the availability of feedback, with the help of which students will be able to immediately find out the correctness of the chosen option);

- the principle of consistency (implies considering the content of the presentation as a system with a structure: highlighting sections);

- the principle of differentiated approach (implies providing various methods and techniques of work depending on the typology of the disorder);

- the principle of clarity (implies the use of illustrations, demonstrations, vivid examples, which contribute to a huge impact on children and the speed of assimilation of the material).

The listed principles act as a support/guideline for selecting materials required for inclusion in a multimedia presentation for developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments.

In accordance with the task being solved, the developed multimedia presentation is pragmatic, since defining the content will allow creating a model on the basis of which presentations will be developed for developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments. Here, several stages can be distinguished, according to which a cognitive model of a multimedia presentation is developed for developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments.

We have defined the following components of multimedia presentation slides for use in developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments, related to providing its users with information:

- *Title*
- *Methodological information;*
- *Technical information;*
- *Task;*
- *Types of assistance;*
- *Encouragement.*

It should also be taken into account when creating a multimedia presentation by a speech therapist in the Power Point program, first it is necessary to do significant preliminary work. This will allow, on the one hand, to exclude the influence of possible technical difficulties on the process of creating a computer

training exercise; on the other hand, it will prevent possible passion for various multimedia elements. The training exercise assumes a diagnostic basis, i.e. first, during a speech therapy examination, the skill that needs to be developed in a junior schoolchild with speech disorders through a system of special exercises is determined. The definition of this skill determines both the topic of the exercise itself (for example, "Sound S") and the specific task of speech therapy work (for example, "Develop the ability to highlight the sound S at the beginning of a word"). Then the speech therapist must predict the possible difficulties that a junior schoolchild with speech disorders may experience in the process of mastering this skill in order to think over different types of assistance that contribute to the successful completion of the task. Finally, the speech therapist should select a similar task that will not only consolidate this skill, but also assess the ability to transfer the demonstrated method of mental action. After the preliminary work has been done, in which all the visual material has been preliminarily collected. Checking with the developed presentation development template, places all the objects on the slides, taking into account the rules of composition and graphic design. Next, sets up the animation of objects and slides, using for this, for example, such technical capabilities of the Power Point program as triggers, hyperlinks, clicks, arbitrary slide show, hidden slide. The teacher should constantly use the opportunity to play an unfinished presentation in order to identify the need to edit its script. At the same time, one must not forget about the need to constantly save the changes made to the presentation. The proposed algorithm for creating educational exercises by a speech therapist using the Microsoft Power Point program will, in our opinion, not only facilitate the process of developing a presentation structure, but also improve the quality and variety of independently developed computer products. Thus, based on the theoretical analysis, we have developed a model of a multimedia presentation for developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments. It is substantive, because the subject of modeling is the content of the multimedia presentation, and pragmatic, because other multimedia presentations for developing sound analysis and synthesis in students with speech impairments can be developed on its basis.

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